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Information Literacy Skills Of Library Staff And Their Influence On Service Delivery In Public Universities In Benue State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated information literacy skills of library staff and their influence on service delivery in public universities in Benue State, Nigeria. The study had two research questions and a hypothesis. They were anchored on Diffusion of Information Theory (1962) by Everett Rogers as well as Human Capital Theory (1964) by Becker. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The area of study was Benue State, specifically in Public University libraries in Benue State including Francis Sulemanu Idachaba Library of Joseph SarwuanTarka University, Makurdi, Rev. Fr. Moses OrshioAdasu, University Library, Makurdi and Federal University of Health Sciences, Otukpo. The population of the study was 229 library staff while census method was employed. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Information Literacy Skills for Service Delivery (ILSSD). The research instruments were validated by three experts. It was trial-tested by twentyfive library staff of University of Mkar, Mkar. The university library chosen has the same characteristics with university libraries in the study area. Data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha method to determine internal consistency of the items of the instruments. The overall reliability of the instrument showed a result of 0.94. The findings of the study revealed that library staff in public universities in Benue State possessed moderate to high levels of IL skills, especially in areas such as online searching, data retrieval, document and referencing, the fourth findings shows that, library staff acquire IL skills through multiple avenues, with workshops, seminars, mentorship, self-study, and on-the-job learning being the most common. Also, the second objective which investigated influence of information literacy skills on service delivery as well as the hypothesis confirmed that possession of IL skills positively influence service delivery outcomes. Finally, it was concluded that information literacy skills are indispensable for the effective performance of library staff in public universities in Benue State.

Keywords: Information literacy, Digital literacy, Skills, Library service, University libraries

INTRODUCTION

In today's dynamic, information-driven world, knowledge has emerged as a vital resource that underpins innovation, education, governance and economic development. The rapid expansion of digital

technologies and the increasing ubiquity of information and communication technologies (ICTs) have significantly altered the landscape of information access and dissemination across the globe. Educational institutions, particularly universities, are at the forefront of this transformation, leveraging digital tools and information systems to facilitate academic excellence, research output and community engagement. These changes demand that institutional support systems especially academic libraries adapt their roles, infrastructure and competencies to support emerging academic needs (Lloyd & Wilkinson, 2017).

Academic libraries, once seen as passive repositories of books and journals, are now transforming themselves as strategic partners in research, teaching and learning. This evolution involves not only the acquisition of advanced ICT infrastructure but also the development of a highly skilled workforce capable of navigating complex information environments. In this regard, the competence and responsiveness of library staff have become central to the effectiveness of academic service delivery. This shift is particularly relevant in developing countries like Nigeria, where digital inclusion and access to quality information services are still emerging. Despite growing investments in digital infrastructure, university libraries in Nigeria often face challenges such as underfunding, limited access to online resources and human resource capacity gaps (Ikonne, Ibikunle, & Babalola, 2023). These issues highlight the need for a deeper understanding of how library staff skills especially information literacy competencies impact service delivery in public universities.

Service delivery in academic institutions refers to the mechanisms through which libraries and other support systems provide timely and relevant access to resources, guidance and technical assistance. Within academic libraries, service delivery encompasses core functions such as book lending, reference support, bibliographic instruction, information literacy training, access to online databases and research consultation services. In addition to traditional services like book lending and reference service, libraries now offer access to digital collections, institutional repositories, e-journals, plagiarism detection tools, virtual reference desks and online learning platforms. Libraries also engage with users via social media, develop subject guides, host workshops on academic writing and citation management and provide remote access to digital archives (Ashikuzzaman, 2023; Rafiq et al., 2021). As the volume of information continues to grow and user needs become more complex, academic libraries are required to adopt innovative, user-centred and flexible service models. Libraries that fail to do so risk obsolescence, especially within university settings where knowledge generation and use are critical (Rafiq et al., 2021).

Ashwin (2020) defines universities as multidisciplinary institutions that not only deliver degrees but also contribute to societal development by equipping individuals with the skills and knowledge needed to address contemporary challenges. Public universities, in particular, play a crucial role in democratising access to information and education. Funded and managed by the government, they cater to large student populations and are mandated to promote national development goals, including social equity, innovation and human capital formation (Martínez-Virto & Pérez-Eransas, 2021).

University libraries are integral to the academic mission of higher institutions, designed to provide faculty, students and researchers with access to both print and digital resources tailored to meet diverse learning and scholarly demands. These libraries are staffed by professional librarians, para-professionals and non-professionals, each of whom contributes to the overall service delivery system. Professional staff, typically with degrees in Library and Information Science handle complex tasks such as cataloguing, database management, information literacy instruction and digital resource curation. Para-professional staff, often holders of diploma or other formal training in library science, assist in circulation, shelving and user assistance. Non-professional staff perform essential support roles including administrative tasks, security and facility maintenance (Manzo & Kannan, 2021). However, for these personnel to function effectively in today's information-rich environment, they require robust information literacy skills that allow them to identify, retrieve, evaluate and apply information ethically and efficiently.

Information literacy is a critical competence that enables individuals to navigate, interpret and use information in a purposeful and ethical manner. It is defined as the ability to identify information needs, locate relevant data, evaluate source credibility and apply knowledge effectively to specific tasks (Adeniran & Onuoha, 2018). In the context of academic libraries, information literacy extends beyond

personal knowledge to include teaching and supporting users in their own information-seeking processes. According to the Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL, 2016), information literacy forms the foundation for lifelong learning and civic participation, enabling individuals to become critical consumers and ethical producers of information. Library staff, therefore, need to be equipped not only to access and evaluate information but also to instruct others, especially students and researchers, on how to do so. These skills are particularly crucial in an age marked by digital disinformation, information overload and the increasing complexity of online scholarly communication.

Benue State in north-central Nigeria is home to three public universities: Rev. Fr. Moses OrshioAdasu University, Makurdi, a state-owned institution established in 1992; Joseph SarwuanTarka University, Makurdi (formerly the University of Agriculture), a federally funded institution; and the Federal University of Health Sciences, Otukpo (FUHSO). Each of these institutions maintains a university library tasked with supporting academic activities. These libraries employ various cadres of staff who are expected to meet the growing and diverse information needs of students, faculty and researchers. However, anecdotal evidence and preliminary observations suggest that limited staff training and gaps in information literacy competencies are undermining the quality and consistency of library service delivery in these institutions.

Ovie and Emumekpor (2023) investigated librarians' digital skills and management of electronic resources in federal university libraries in South-south, Nigeria. The main objective of the study is to examine the relationship between librarians' digital skills and the management of electronic resources in university libraries. The study's findings revealed that librarians in federal university libraries in South-south, Nigeria, possess various digital skills; the extent of possession of digital skills by the librarians in federal university libraries in South-south, Nigeria is very high; and that there is a significant relationship between librarians' digital skills and effective management of electronic resources in university libraries.

Ikonne, Ibikunle and Babalola (2023) studied the influence of information literacy skills on library service delivery in public universities in South-West Nigeria. The study found that librarians possessed high levels of information literacy skills, particularly in the areas of identifying, evaluating, and using information ethically. A significant positive relationship was established between librarians' information literacy skills and effective library service delivery. The study concluded that librarians' proficiency in information literacy is a major determinant of quality service delivery in university libraries.

Agbro and Agbro (2024) investigated digital literacy skills and job performance of librarians in federal and state university libraries in South-South, Nigeria. It was found that electronic mailing skills of librarians predicted their job performance by 96% implying a high prediction. This means that an increase in electronic mailing skills will lead to a corresponding increase in the job performance of librarians and vice versa. The findings revealed that the relationship that existed between all the digital literacy skills and job performance of librarians in federal and state university libraries in South-South, Nigeria is high.

Therefore, this study sought to investigate the influence of information literacy skills on service delivery by library staff in public universities in Benue State, there by identifying the information literacy skills possessed by library staff and determining the influence of information literacy skills of library staff on service delivery in public universities in Benue State.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory by Everett Rogers (1962) and Human Capital theory by Becker (1964), collectively provide a solid foundation for understanding both the development and application of information literacy skills in the context of service delivery by library staff.

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI), proposed by Everett M. Rogers in 1962, provides a conceptual model for understanding how new ideas, practices, or technologies are adopted within a social system. The theory defines diffusion as “ the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the members of a social system” (Rogers, 2003). In university library settings, the acquisition and application of information literacy skills such as the ability to locate, evaluate and apply information effectively can be viewed as a form of innovation.

The Human Capital Theory, developed by Theodore Schultz in the early 1960s and later formalized by Gary S. Becker (1964), is a prominent economic and sociological framework that emphasizes the value of

investing in people to enhance their productivity and societal contribution. The theory rests on the premise that individuals possess attributes such as knowledge, skills, experiences and health that can be enhanced through intentional investment, there by increasing their efficiency and value in the labour market or professional environment. In the context of this study, Human Capital Theory provides a robust analytical framework for examining how the knowledge and competencies of library staff directly influence the quality of services they render. Here, library staff serves as human capital whose effectiveness is tied to their capacity to access, process and disseminate information efficiently. Information literacy skills, as the core competency under investigation, represent the human capital investment that institutions must make to ensure quality service delivery.

The integration of Diffusion of Innovation Theory (Rogers, 1962) and Human Capital Theory (Becker, 1964) provides a complementary and multidimensional framework for analysing the influence of information literacy skills on service delivery by library staff in public universities. In summary, merging the two theories creates a holistic framework for analysing both the capacity and behavioural components of library service delivery.

RESEARCH METHODS

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The area of study was Benue State, specifically done in Public University libraries in Benue State including Francis Sulemanu Idachaba Library of Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Rev. Fr. Moses OrshioAdasu, University Library, Makurdi and Federal University of Health Sciences, Otuokpo. The population of the study was 229 library staff while census method for data collection was used. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while Chi-square was used to test hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The analysis is presented in line with the research questions and null hypotheses that guided the study.

Research Question 1: *What are the information literacy skills possessed by staff of public universities in Benue State?*

Table 1: Information literacy skills possessed by staff of public universities in Benue State

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	StD	Decision
1	Creating and editing of documents using software skills	82	106	4	17	3.27	.69	Agree
2	Data Storage Skills	78	118	1	12	3.31	.60	Agree
3	Retrieval Skills	94	109	1	5	3.42	.57	Agree
4	Searching for Information Online Skills	100	101	1	7	3.44	.59	Agree
5	Creating of power point presentation skills	84	120	0	5	3.38	.53	Agree
6	Delivery and Presentation Skills	68	133	1	7	3.28	.55	Agree
7	Reference skills	79	125	1	4	3.35	.54	Agree
Cluster Mean						3.35	084	Agree

The results in Table 3 reveal that staff possess a wide range of IL skills, although the levels vary. The highest levels of possession were reported for retrieval skills (M = 3.42, SD = 0.57) and online searching skills (M = 3.44, SD = 0.59). In contrast, relatively weaker competencies were found in document creation and editing (M = 3.27, SD = 0.69) and presentation/delivery skills (M = 3.28, SD = 0.55). The findings suggest that while staff are proficient in information handling and access-related tasks, there is a

relative deficit in skills that require creativity, technical writing, or instructional delivery. This imbalance has implications for how effectively staff can contribute to training, outreach, and advanced scholarly support.

Research Question 2: *What is the influence of information literacy skills of library staff on service delivery in public universities in Benue State?*

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of respondents on influence of information literacy skills of library staff on service delivery in public universities in Benue State

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	SD	D	Mean(StD	Decision.
8	Improved access to information	85	110	5	9	3.32	.67	Agree
9	Efficient use of ICT tools	95	10	0	4	3.39	.67	Agree
10	Increased productivity	109	83	6	11	3.41	.72	Agree
11	Better user satisfaction	105	93	2	9	3.44	.63	Agree
12	Higher quality information dissemination	102	99	2	6	3.44	.60	Agree
13	Effective training and guidance	103	99	0	7	3.46	.56	Agree
14	Better decision making	96	105	0	8	3.42	.57	Agree
Cluster Mean						2.57		High Extent

The result presented in Table 2 establish that information literacy skills exert a substantial influence on the quality of service delivery. The highest rated influence was effective training and guidance (M = 3.46, SD = 0.56), followed closely by user satisfaction (M = 3.44, SD = 0.63) and high-quality information dissemination (M = 3.44, SD = 0.60). Other significant outcomes include improved decision-making, enhanced productivity, and more efficient use of ICT tools. These findings reinforce the argument that IL competencies are not merely auxiliary to library functions but constitute a central determinant of staff effectiveness.

Test of Hypothesis

Table 3: Chi-Square Analysis on the Significance of information literacy skills possessed on service delivery by public University libraries staff in Benue State.

Responses	Fo	Fe	Df	χ^2	p	Remark
Strongly Agree	84	65.0				
Agree	116	65.0				
Disagree	8	65.0	3	69.053	0.001	Significant
Strongly Disagree	1	65.0				
Total	209					

Table 3 shows that the chi-square result was $\chi^2 = 69.053$, $p < 0.001$. Since $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that the skills possessed by staff significantly influence their ability to deliver services effectively. The descriptive findings in Table 1 corroborate this result, showing that staff with higher competence in retrieval ($\bar{x} = 3.42$, StD = 0.57) and online searching ($\bar{x} = 3.44$, StD = 0.59) also demonstrated stronger service outcomes such as supporting academic research and facilitating access to resources.

DISCUSSION

The study's first objective was concerned with information literacy skills possessed by staff. The findings here revealed that library staff in public universities in Benue State generally possess moderate to high levels of IL skills, especially in areas such as online searching, data retrieval, document creation, and referencing. However, competencies in presentation and advanced referencing were comparatively

weaker. The finding supports Ovie and Emumejakpor (2023), who documented similar disparities in skill possession among librarians in the South-South, with stronger digital competencies in some areas and deficiencies in others.

The findings on the second objective which investigated influence of information literacy skills on service delivery confirmed that IL skills positively influence service delivery outcomes. Staff with higher IL competence reported improvements in access to information, more efficient ICT use, increased productivity, enhanced user satisfaction, and better decision-making. This finding mirrors the work of Agbro and Agbro (2024) who reported that librarians' digital literacy strongly predicted their job performance, reinforcing the argument that IL skills are indispensable to professional effectiveness. By situating IL within staff service delivery rather than just student outcomes, the present study broadens the scope of existing literature. It demonstrates that IL is not only a user competency but also a staff requirement that directly improves institutional effectiveness.

The hypothesis testing confirmed that IL skills possessed significantly influence service delivery. This rejects the null hypothesis and underscores that staff who have mastered IL competencies are more effective in delivering quality services. The result is in agreement with Ikonne et al. (2023), who established that the level of staff competence in IL strongly predicts the quality of library services. By focusing on Benue State, the present study expands empirical understanding of the Nigerian context, showing that skill possession rather than skill requirement is the crucial factor in enhancing service delivery.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that information literacy skills are indispensable for the effective performance of library staff in public universities in Benue State. This suggests that information literacy should be addressed holistically, considering not only individual competence but also the enabling environment in which librarians operate.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Universities should institutionalise continuous professional development programmes, including workshops, seminars, and refresher courses, to ensure that library staff continually update and deepen their IL competencies.
2. Special attention should be given to areas of weakness such as presentation, communication, and document creation skills, which are critical for user education and academic support.
3. While workshops and on-the-job learning are important, universities should encourage staff to also utilise self-study and online platforms. Subsidised access to professional online training resources could strengthen self-directed learning.

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